

HERITAGE SCENT DEVELOPMENT REPORT

PART
2

This worksheet is part of a sequence of worksheets to assist the development and creation of a heritage scent for the use of olfactory storytelling.

PART 1 Heritage Scent Design Brief

PART 2 *Heritage Scent Development Report*

This form provides the opportunity for the scent designer to reflect on the creation of a scent intended for olfactory storytelling. This includes the process and the materials used for the scent development. The document is to be filled out by the scent designer. A Heritage Scent Development Report should be created for *every heritage scent created*, regardless if it is intended for the same exhibition/project/event.

PROJECT DETAILS

TITLE OF EXHIBITION/PROJECT/ EVENT FOR WHICH THE SMELL IS INTENDED:	
INSTITUTION:	
LOCATION:	
PROJECTED TEST TOUR DATE:	
PROJECTED OPENING DATE:	
TOTAL NUMBER OF SMELLS:	
SCENT DISTRIBUTION METHOD(S):	
PERSON OF CONTACT:	

PROFILE OF THE SCENT DESIGNER

NAME:	
COMPANY/INSTITUTION:	

1. Do you specialise in a certain type of olfactory design? (e.g. perfumes, air fresheners, detergents)

RESPONSE:

HERITAGE SCENT DESCRIPTION

2. For which artwork/artefact/smellscape is this made for?

RESPONSE:

3. Please provide a description of your scent creation. (e.g intensity, hedonic tone, notes)

RESPONSE:

4. What narrative do you want to achieve through your scent creation?

RESPONSE:

5. What is the olfactory pyramid of the smell? (e.g. top, middle, base notes)

Olfactory Pyramid

Top:

Middle:

Base:

6. What are the materials/notes of the smell? (e.g. clove, spicy)

RESPONSE:

7. Please provide the formula for your scent creation (if applicable).

- Please provide the name of the company who created the scent (IFF, GIV, FIR) & the code (e.g. CAS Number, FEMA) of the ingredient (if applicable)
- Please provide the weight percentage of each ingredient

INGREDIENT	COMPANY / CODE	WEIGHT
(example) Truffle black base 10% dpg	PCW	25

PERSONAL SCENT DESIGN PROCESS AND EVALUATION

8. Did you conduct research or make site visits to design the smell?

RESPONSE:

9. How does your creation compare to the historic description/recipe provided in the *Heritage Scent Design Brief*? (e.g. did you omit or add materials to the historical recipe?)

RESPONSE:

10. What components of the brief did you concentrate on?

RESPONSE:

11. How many versions did you develop?

RESPONSE:

SIGNED OFF BY	
DATE	

Next steps for the scent designer:

- Provide a copy of this document to the person of contact.
- Plan a meeting with the person of contact where you review the document together.
- Upon providing the heritage scent samples, make sure you provide (1) a completed *Part 2: Heritage Scent Development Report*; (2) the safety sheet.

Note: account time for at least one evaluation round.